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Development of Lignin-Modified Phenol-Formaldehyde Resins: Sustainability Effect in the Furniture Industry

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Abstract

The primary aim of bio-based energy production is to achieve sustainable energy generation by utilizing biological waste as raw material. These materials are processed through various conversion technologies in biorefineries, where research has demonstrated the feasibility of producing petroleum-derived products from biological resources. Among them, lignin—a renewable phenolic macromolecule found in the cell walls of biomass, possessing aromatic rings and phenolic hydroxyl groups similar to phenol—has attracted significant attention as a promising substitute for phenol in PF resin adhesives, particularly in the wood and furniture industries where such resins are widely applied. By modifying lignin to develop lignin-modified PF resin adhesives, it is possible to achieve notable performance improvements while simultaneously enhancing economic efficiency and reducing environmental impact. In this study, lignin-modified phenol-formaldehyde (LPF) resins were synthesized, with lignin selected as a bio-based alternative to phenol owing to its aromatic structure, phenolic hydroxyl groups, and natural abundance. The synthesis was carried out by using two different lignin types, kraft lignin and organosolv lignin, by substituting phenol with lignin at 50-60-70 to 80% wt. ratios. The experiments focused on evaluating the influence of lignin type on the extent of phenol substitution. Following synthesis, the resins were characterized in terms of dynamic viscosity and molecular weight with potential applications in environmentally friendly and sustainable adhesives for the furniture sector.

Keywords: Furniture, kraft lignin, lignin-modified phenol-formaldehyde, organosolv lignin, sustainability

1. Introduction

Fossil fuel consumption has existed for many decades (Solarte-Toro & Cardona Alzate, 2023). But we know that fossil fuels are both highly harmful to environmental pollution and are decreasing day by day because they are not a renewable energy source. For this reason, various researches are being carried out every day to obtain biologically based energy by reducing fossil

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fuel consumption. Especially in order to reduce fossil fuel consumption, which has a great economic impact, the trend towards sustainable resources such as bioenergy and biofuels is increasing day by day (Al Mubarak, Rezaee, & Wood, 2024).

The main goal of bio-based energy production is based on sustainable energy production by using biological wastes as raw materials. Biological raw materials are transformed through various conversion processes in so-called biorefineries, enabling the use of a renewable raw material to produce clean energy that is environmentally friendly (Katakojwala & Mohan, 2021).

As a result of theoretical and practical research, it has been determined that it is possible to obtain petroleum-based products with biological raw materials. However, the end product obtained is not economically advantageous compared to petroleum-based products. There are 4 biorafinary types such as lignocellulosic feedstock biorefinery, whole plant, green biorefineries, biorefinery two-platform concept (Clark & Deswarte, 2015). Lignocellulosic feedstock type of biorafinary produces lignin and subsequently depolymerised lignin (Uihlein & Schebek, 2009).

Lignin:

Lignin, one of the most abundant natural polymers in nature, is one of the by-products of chemical processes, especially in the paper industry. This is because the primary source of cellulose is lignocellulosic biomass (Ragauskas et al., 2014). This bio-based feedstock consists of lignin, cellulose, and hemicellulose. Structurally, lignin is a polyphenolic macromolecule with *p*-hydroxyphenyl (H), guaiacyl (G), and syringyl (S) monomers as the three phenyl-propene units (Boerjan, Ralph, & Baucher, 2003). These units are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Structures of monolignols: *p*-hydroxyphenyl (H); guaiacyl (G); syringyl (S) monomers

The reactivity of lignin depends on structural elements such as aliphatic hydroxyl, methoxy, carboxyl and carbonyl groups, but the structural composition and properties vary depending on the source and isolation method (Hatakeyama & Hatakeyama, 2009).

Lignin can provide a variety of aromatic building blocks with high added value. With its aromatic basic structure, lignin is theoretically the most suitable renewable resource to replace aromatics from petrochemicals. In practice, however, this has not yet materialized because the valorization of lignin faces several challenges (Graglia, Kanna, & Esposito, 2015).

Lignin Extraction from Lignocellulosic Biomass:

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There are different methods for lignin extraction such as kraft, sulfite, soda and organosolv. The most common of these methods is the kraft method, which meets 85% of lignin needs worldwide. The organosolv process is considered to be much more environmentally friendly than the kraft process due to its sulfur-free and easier process conditions. Although the organosolv process provides high purity lignin, it has only been commercially produced for a few years (Carvajal, Gómez, & Cardona, 2016).

Lignin shows structural changes depending on the type of process used and therefore exhibits different chemical properties. Organosolv lignin contains a large proportion of β -O-4 bonds and is almost insoluble in water and organic solvents. It is the most natural form of technical lignin as the core structure remains mostly unchanged. In contrast, lignin from the kraft process has a condensed structure with few C-C cross-links. It therefore develops chemical resistance to hydrolysis. Another disadvantage is that it contains sulfur in the form of thiols, which can poison catalysts in further processing steps (Watkins, Nuruddin, Hosur, Tcherbi-Narteh, & Jeelani, 2015).

Phenol Formaldehyde (PF) Resin:

Phenol formaldehyde (PF) resins are polymeric compounds. This compound is synthesized by acid or base catalyzed polycondensation of phenol and formaldehyde. To prepare the resin, formaldehyde is first added to phenol. Then condensation reaction is applied and finally curing processes are applied. Curing takes place at high temperature and requires further condensation reactions and molecular rearrangements (Pizzi & Ibeh, 2022).

The wood industry is one of the largest consumers of PF resins. With their high mechanical performance, stable molding processing performance, good flame resistance, long-term thermal and mechanical stability, satisfactory electrical and thermal insulation properties, high adhesion strength and moisture resistance, PF resins are preferred and used in many areas. Resoller is the preferred type of PF resin for wood bonding due to their ability to form three-dimensional networks with favorable mechanical performance when cured, unlike novolaks, which are thermoplastic and require an additional curing agent. However, the resins need to undergo chemical modification to remain a viable option in an increasingly environmentally conscious industry (Dunky, 2017).

Lignin Modified Phenol Formaldehyde (LPF) Resin:

Improved performance of lignin for the production of value-added products can be achieved by converting it into molecules with lower molecular weight through depolymerization. The process yields aromatic and phenolic molecules with greater structural similarity to phenol (Fernández-Rodríguez, Erdocia, Sánchez, Alriols, & Labidi, 2017). This makes depolymerized lignin a promising alternative to phenol as it allows for higher degrees of substitution.

Substitution of phenol with lignin until 50 % wt. is possible without sacrificing resin quality. Further substitution requires either structural modification of lignin, or pretreatment methods during synthesis. Methylation, phenolation, and thermolysis techniques increase the reactivity of lignin molecules. Methylation and phenolation involve lignin pretreatment with formaldehyde or phenol respectively, before entering the resinification reaction. These methods introduce reactive functional groups into the structure of lignin, while thermolysis induces targeted structural degradation. Thermo-chemical depolymerization by pyrolysis, oxidation, hydrogenolysis, and hydrolysis necessitate application of heat under specific reaction conditions, cleaving intermolecular bonds. Depolymerization yields phenolic oligomers with

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decreased molecular weight (M_w) and reduced aliphatic hydroxyl groups, which have higher structural similarity to phenol, serving as an ideal substitute for phenol in LPF production (Sarkar & Adhikari, 2000).

2. Materials and Methods

Materials and Chemicals:

All materials and chemicals used during the experiments are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. List of materials and chemicals used in the experiment

Materials	Chemicals
• Beakers	• Phenol, C_6H_6O
• Reflux Condenser	• Kraft Lignin
• 3 Necked Round Bottom Flask	• Organosolv Lignin
• Dropping Funnel	• Sodium Hydroxide, NaOH (50 %)
• Spatulas	• Formaldehyde Solution (37 %, for synthesis)
• Funnel	• Water, H_2O (Distilled)
• Glass Plug	
• Sample Tube	
• Magnetic Fish	

Experimental Part:

Experiments were started with the same amount of lignin and phenol (both 50%). After than amount of lignin increased each step and therefore amount of phenol decreased at the same time. The increment and decrement values of both were changed by 10% at each step. According to this change, four different experiments were performed with lignin content of 50%, 60%, 70 %, 80%. Also the amount of other chemicals was kept constant. These experimental steps were performed with two different types of lignin such as kraft lignin and organosolv lignin. The first 4 experiments were performed with kraft lignin and the last 4 experiments were performed with organosolv lignin. All of the chemical amounts are listed in Table 2 for each experiment step. Also in this table kraft lignin was called KC1202 and the organosolv lignin was called KC1196.

Table 2. Chemical amounts used in the experiment

Experiment Name	Lignin Type	Phenol Amount (g)	Lignin Amount (g)	NaOH Amount (g)	Formaldehyde Amount (g)	H_2O Amount (g)
K-LP-50 %	KC1202	15.39	15.35	13.11	34.42	21.80
K-LP-60 %	KC1202	12.33	18.46	13.11	34.42	21.80
K-LP-70 %	KC1202	9.20	21.49	13.11	34.42	21.80
K-LP-80 %	KC1202	6.16	24.03	13.11	34.42	21.80
O-LP-50 %	KC1196	15.39	15.35	13.11	34.42	21.80
O-LP-60 %	KC1196	12.33	18.46	13.11	34.42	21.80
O-LP-70 %	KC1196	9.20	21.49	13.11	34.42	21.80
O-LP-80 %	KC1196	6.16	24.03	13.11	34.42	21.80

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In the experimental procedure, the order of addition of chemicals, process temperature, and time conditions are shown schematically in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the experimental process

During the experiments, 2 points were very important.

- Lignin addition should be very slow. Because when lignin is added rapidly, it does not dissolve and agglomerations are seen.
- The addition of formaldehyde should also be very slow. Fast formaldehyde addition causes foaming.

Analysis Part:

Dynamic viscosity (rheometry) and gel permeation chromatography (GPC) were performed on all resins obtained from the experiments.

Dynamic viscosity (rheometry) analysis; An air-carried Anton Paar Modular Compact Rheometer (MCR) 102 equipped with a CP50-1 conical plate (diameter: 50 mm; angle of inclination: 1°) device was used to obtain the ratio coefficient between the dynamic viscosity η and shear rate of LPF resins. Measurements were performed at a constant temperature of 30°C in rotation mode.

GPC analysis; Thermo Fisher Dionex ICS 1500+ gel permeation chromatography consisted pre-column PSS MCX Guard (dimensions: 50 x 8 mm) and three PSS Analytical columns (Specifications: 100A/1000A/100 000A, dimensions: 300 mm x 8 mm) device was used to obtain the molecular weight distribution of LPF resin samples. In the analysis, 1 mg sample was dissolved in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaOH to obtain 1 mg mL⁻¹ concentration of samples. After than the mixture filtered with 0.45 μ m syringe filter. During the analysis, the flow rate was set to 1 mL min⁻¹, column temperature 50°C, injection volume 10 μ L and injection time 33 min. The UV detector (VWD) was also set to a wavelength of 280 nm for the samples.

3. Findings and Discussion

Dynamic viscosity (rheometry) analysis results:

All resins were analysed for their dynamic viscosity. All data are presented in Figure 3.

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Figure 3. Graph of dynamic viscosity analysis

Resins containing Kraft Lignin showed higher viscosity values than organosolv resins. There are several reasons for this behaviour. Softwood Kraft Lignin reveals a high concentration of guaiacyl substituents in their polymer backbone which leads to higher reactivity in resin condensation reactions. In addition, Kraft Lignin always have higher molecular weight than Organosolv Lignin. Organosolv Lignin is usually originating from annuary plants with low contents of lignin. The organosolv process offers milder conditions without harsh acidic or basic treatment as in the Kraft process or Sulphite process. Therefore, a higher content of less reactive substituents (e.g. Sinapyl units) due to its original plants and also higher steric hindering is the key for slower viscosity increase in resin cooking.

GPC analyses of the used lignins:

From the used Kraft-Lignin and Organosolv-Lignin have been determined the molecular weight distribution. The results are given in Table 3 and Figure 4.

Table 3. Reference results of GPC analysis for kraft lignin and organosolv lignin

	M_N	M_w	PDI
Kraft Lignin	908 (± 2)	4450 (± 15)	4.90 (± 0.01)
Organosolv Lignin	665 (± 2)	1770 (± 6)	2.65 (± 0.01)

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Figure 4. Reference graph of GPC analysis for kraft lignin and organosolv lignin

GPC analyses results of the produced resins:

All resins were analysed for their molecular weight distribution. All data are presented in Figure 5, 6 and Table 4, 5.

Figure 5. Graph of GPC analysis for kraft lignin-resins

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Table 4. Results of GPC analysis for kraft lignin-resins

Sample Name	M _N	M _w	PDI
Kraft Lignin 50 %	725 (±4)	2054 (±10)	2.83 (±0.02)
Kraft Lignin 60 %	738 (±3)	2268 (±9)	3.07 (±0.03)
Kraft Lignin 70 %	740 (±4)	2340 (±12)	3.16 (±0.02)
Kraft Lignin 80 %	755 (±7)	2572 (±14)	3.40 (±0.04)

Figure 6. Graph of GPC analysis for organosolv lignin-resins

Table 5. Results of GPC analysis for organosolv lignin-resins

Sample Name	M _N	M _w	PDI
Organosolv Lignin 50 %	510 (±2)	1295 (±8)	2.53 (±0.01)
Organosolv Lignin 60 %	521 (±3)	1384 (±10)	2.65 (±0.02)
Organosolv Lignin 70 %	535 (±2)	1438 (±11)	2.68 (±0.01)
Organosolv Lignin 80 %	538 (±2)	1502 (±16)	2.79 (±0.05)

GPC analysis results show that M_N, M_w and polydispersity values increase with higher lignin substitution. These values are higher in Kraft Lignin than in Organosolv Lignin. This is in correlation with both the GPC results of lignins and viscosity results of produced resins.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

Adhesives commonly used in the wood industry are phenolic resins. The reasons for the widespread use of PF resins in the industry include their high strength, resistance to moisture, resistance to heat and chemicals, and high thermal stability. On the other hand, PF resins are toxic due to being a petrochemical product. Furthermore, they have negative environmental

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impacts as they are obtained from non-renewable resources. For all these reasons, this study was carried out to investigate the feasibility of using lignin material, which is structurally very similar to phenol, as an alternative.

In experimental studies, kraft and organosolv lignin types were used as substitute materials for phenol at ratios ranging from 50% to 80%. Afterwards, dynamic viscosity and GPC analysis were applied to the resulting lignin-modified phenol formaldehyde resins. All research results indicated that lignin could be used as a substitute material for phenol at ratios up to 80%.

Thanks and Information Note

The article complies with national and international research and publication ethics.

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